

Evaluation of chemical constituents in aqueous wood ash extracts of *Azadirachta indica* (neem) and *Parkia biglobosa* (locust bean)

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ABSTRACT

The use of wood ash extracts as food additives and for medicinal purposes by Gbagyi people and other ethnic groups in the Middle-Belt Region of Nigeria, with dearth of information on its chemical constituents has remained a traditional practice. There is scarcity of information on the inorganic and organic composition and toxicity potentials of aqueous wood-ash extracts. This study reported the phytochemical parameters, heavy metals and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons present in aqueous wood ashes extracts of *Azadirachta indica* and *Parkia biglobosa*. The local method of ash extraction by Gbagyi people was used, using water and phytochemicals, heavy metals and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHS) screened and analysed by methods described by Eleazu et al. (2012), Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer and Gas Chromatography respectively. Alkaloids, Cardenolides, Cardiac glycosides, carbohydrates and terpenoid were present in both extracts, while saponins, tannins, sterols, quinones and amino acids were only present in *P. biglobosa*. Heavy metals; Cu (83.53 and 91.64), Pb (21.68 and 24.19), As (8.96 and 6.77), Cd (1.95 and 1.64), Zn (88.91 and 72.74), Ni (9.91 and 7.467) and Co (2.73 and 2.13) ppm were present in *A. indica* and *P. biglobosa* respectively, above standard limits. PAHS concentrations were so high in both extracts. An aqueous wood ash extracts of *A. indica* and *P. biglobosa* content toxic chemicals that could have deleterious effects on body organs or tissues and can compromise human health.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The use of wood ash extracts as food additive and for medicinal purposes have been a continuous practice among Gbagyi people and other ethnic groups in the Middle-Belt Region of Nigeria.

Wood ash is the inorganic and organic residue remaining after the combustion of wood. As a result of the oxidation processes during combustion, the wood ash generated retains the overall composition of the mineral nutrients contained in the wood, with the exception of nitrogen compounds, which are mainly released into the gas phase [1]. The physical and chemical composition of ash contents are variable among tree species and also depend

on soil type and climate. They vary significantly depending upon the method and manner of combustion, efficiency of the boiler, and other supplementary fuel used with wood [2, 3]. Wood-ash is a by-product of wood burning which is classed as a form of green energy production because it is both carbons neutral and renewable. When wood is burned, the organic portion is converted to CO₂ and water while the inorganic portion remains as ash [4, 5]. Wood-ash is used widely across the globe for various purposes that range from washing cooking utensils [6], soap making, biodiesels, poultry and livestock feed processing [7, 8], improving soil fertility [9], food/seeds preservation [10], fermentation processes [11], insecticide [12], pest control and seed treatment to increase yield [9, 13, 14], inhibition of growth

of some phytopathogenic and mycotoxigenic fungi [15] and ripening of fruits. Among the Gbagyi, Nupe, Epira and other groups of people, some of the major ethnic groups in North-Central Nigeria/Middle-Belt region, wood ash is also used for preparing foods like tuwo (meal prepared using maize/corn flour) and as medicine for stomach ache.

Wood-ash contains all the essential plant nutrients except nitrogen (N), which is vaporized during the combustion [16]. In addition to the valuable mineral nutrients, wood-ash also contains heavy metals such as lead, zinc and cadmium. The levels of cadmium, lead and zinc, is mostly high enough for wood-ash to fall into the 'toxic waste' category [5].

The consumption of wood-ash extracts, as food additive by some ethnic groups in the Middle-Belt Region of Nigeria without any or adequate knowledge of its inorganic and organic constituents and possible effects on their health has been a continuous practice from time immemorial. Earlier studies on wood-ashes have focused mainly on their uses and environmental impacts; there is dearth of information on the inorganic and organic composition, especially that of neem and African locust bean tree, which are mostly used for fuel, food, medicinal and other essential purposes. Hence, this research reported the phytochemical parameters, heavy metals and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons present in wood ashes extracts of *A. indica* and *P. biglobosa*.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Collection and processing of woods to ashes

Fresh *Azadirachta indica* (neem) and *Parkia biglobosa* (African locust bean) woods were both collected from Katsina and Kaduna States, North-Western Nigeria respectively. This is because of their abundance, availability and easy access in these areas. Stalk of each plant, carrying leaves and flowers, were collected and taken to the herbarium of Department of Biological Sciences, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria for authentication. Voucher numbers of 90051 (*Azadirachta indica*) and 324 (*Parkia biglobosa*) were obtained. The woods, including barks collected were broken into pieces, to fasten the drying process and sun dried for 60days (2 months) before burning to ashes. The woods were separately burnt in open air. Ashes produced were collected in plastic bags and taken to the laboratory for storage and subsequent processing. Use of fuel for burning was avoided to minimize contamination.

2.2 Preparation of wood ash extracts

Ash extraction was carried out using the traditional method practiced by the Gbagyi

people, with some modification. The ashes collected from the burned woods were placed into stainless steel bowls and wetted with University of Ibadan supplied tap water. The bowl, containing the wet ash was heated on hotplate for 120 minutes (2 hours) at a moderate temperature of 40 °C. The ash was later transferred to a perforated bowl, placed on a clean empty container (bowl) that served for collection of extracts. The perforated bowl was underlaid with cloth sieve. The ash in the perforated bowl was stayed for an hour to settle and tap water was poured into the bowl and allowed to percolate into the container. This process was carried out repeatedly until enough extract was collected. The collected aqueous extracts will be further processed using BUCHI Switzerland (Rotavapor R-210) Rotary Evaporator and water bath at 40 °C. The residues were stored in bottles at 5 °C in the laboratory, for subsequent analysis and administration.

2.3 Physicochemical, Heavy Metals and PAHS Analysis

The wood ashes were subjected to phytochemical screening to determine the available phytochemical elements. Alkaloids, saponins, flavonoids, tannins, organic acids, alkalinity, glycosides and antioxidant activities were determined using methods described by [17-20]. Atomic Absorption Spectrometry analyses was used to determine the presence of copper (Cu), Zinc (Zn), Lead (Pb), Cadmium (Cd), Cobalt (Co), Nickel (Ni) and Arsenic (As) as described by (21). Gas Chromatographic Mass Spectrometry analyses were carried out to investigate the presence of Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of phytochemical screening of the wood ash extracts, as presented on Table 1 revealed the presence of alkaloid, cardenolides, cardiac glycosides, carbohydrates and terpenoid in both extracts; while anthraquinones, flavonoid and phenol were absent in both. Saponins, tannins, sterols, quinones and amino acids were only found present in the *Parkia biglobosa* extract.

Results obtained from heavy metal analysis showed Arsenic, Cadmium, Zinc, Nickel and Cobalt to be higher in *A. indica* while Copper and Lead were higher in the *P. biglobosa* (Table 2). As shown on Table 3, results of polycyclic hydrocarbons analysis indicated higher concentrations of Fluoranthene, Pyrene, Benzo (a) anthracene, Benzo (b) Fluoranthene, Benzo (k) Fluoranthene, Benzo (a) pyrene, Indeno (1,2,3 - cd) pyrene and Dibenzo (a, h) anthracene in *A. indica* while Naphthalene, Acenaphthylene, Acenaphthene, Fluorene and Benzo (g, h, i) perylene were higher in *P. biglobosa*.

Table 1. Phytochemical parameters of *A. indica* and *P. biglobosa* wood ashes

Phytochemical	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	<i>Parkia biglobosa</i>
Alkaloid	+ve	+ve
Cardenolides	+ve	+ve
Saponins	-ve	+ve
Tannins	-ve	+ve
Cardiac Glycosides	+ve	+ve
Sterols	-ve	+ve
Carbohydrates	+ve	+ve
Terpenoid	+ve	+ve
Quinones	-ve	+ve
Amino Acids	-ve	+ve

Table 2. Heavy metals concentrations in *A. indica* and *P. biglobosa* wood ashes

Extract	Cu (ppm)	Pb (ppm)	As (ppm)	Cd (ppm)	Zn (ppm)	Ni (ppm)	Co (ppm)
<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	83.5317	21.6842	8.9642	1.9473	88.9064	9.9074	2.7312
<i>Parkia biglobosa</i>	91.6442	24.1963	6.7718	1.6399	72.7431	7.4626	2.1386
FAO/WHO (1989)	30	0.50	-	0.50	40	-	-

FAO/WHO (1989)

Table 3. Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) concentrations in *A. indica* and *P. biglobosa* wood ashes

PAH	<i>A. indica</i> (mg/kg)	<i>P. biglobosa</i> (mg/kg)
Naphthalene	2.84 e ⁻¹	3.12e ⁻¹
Acenaphthylene	3.81 e ⁻¹	4.32 e ⁻¹
Acenaphthene	2.43 e ⁻¹	2.45 e ⁻¹
Fluorene	7.35 e ⁻¹	7.41 e ⁻¹
Phenanthrene	4.61 e ⁻¹	3.45 e ⁻¹
Anthracene	3.70 e ⁻¹	3.39 e ⁻¹
Fluoranthene	3.39	3.03
Pyrene	6.67	5.58
Benzo (a) anthracene	3.36	2.97
Chrysene	4.11	3.38
Benzo (b) Fluoranthene	6.68	5.24
Benzo (k) Fluoranthene	1.41	1.18
Benzo (a) pyrene	1.99	1.59
Indeno (1,2,3 - cd) pyrene	1.25	4.07 e ⁻¹
Dibenzo (a, h) anthracene	1.16	7.43 e ⁻¹
Benzo (g, h, i) perylene	4.41 e ⁻¹	6.96 e ⁻¹

The use of aqueous wood ashes extracts of *A. indica* and *P. biglobosa*, and that of woods is a very common practice among some ethnic groups in the Middle-Belt region of Nigeria. They are used traditionally as food additives and for medicinal purposes in treating stomach ache. Though very rare, wood ash extracts have been said to be used for abortion purpose, which later resulted in permanent infertility to the user after the abortion. There has been scarcity of reports of studies on chemical constituents of aqueous wood ash extracts and their toxic effects in animals.

The results of phytochemical screening in this study indicate the retention of some phytochemicals after combustions of the woods. The presence of alkaloid in the *A. indica* suggest the medicinal potential of the wood ash, which bark, leaves, roots and other parts are widely used for various medicinal purposes. It also implies alkaloid can still be retained by this

wood ash after combustion. Cardenolides are remarkable steroidal toxins that have become model systems, critical in the development of theories for chemical ecology and coevolution, because cardenolides inhibit ubiquitous and essential animal enzyme [22]. The presence of saponin in *P. biglobosa* suggests the extract may be deleterious to user. This is because saponin has the property of precipitating and coagulating red blood cells. Some of the characteristics of saponins include formation of foams in aqueous solutions, haemolytic activity, cholesterol binding properties [23] and bitterness [24]. Tannins are dietary anti-nutrients that are responsible for the astringent taste of foods and drinks [25]. They bind to both proteins and carbohydrates, which has several implications for commodities containing tannins [20]. Cardiac glycosides are highly toxic secondary plant compounds which bind to and specifically inhibit the ubiquitous animal enzyme Na⁺K⁺-ATPase [26].

The heavy metal concentrations that have been recorded in the wood ash are beyond standard permissible limits. The difference in heavy metal concentrations in the two wood (*A. indica* and *P. biglobosa*) ashes might be dependent on the plant species, growth conditions, soil parent material and ash fraction [27, 28]. There are concerns about the potential health effects of some of these elements, or specific forms of these elements, whenever they are present in products that can be ingested, such as foods or dietary supplements. Heavy metals can, in certain quantities, cause disease, be carcinogenic, have adverse reproductive effects, unfavourably impact nutrition, and displace more biologically useful metals such as calcium and zinc [29, 30]. Lead have been indicted to have some deleterious effects observed in liver and kidneys in very high doses of lead administration with some similarities to chronic oral administration of low doses of lead [31].

Although studies in experimental animals on individual PAHs, mainly on benzo(a)pyrene, have shown various toxicological effects, such as haematological effects, reproductive and developmental toxicity and immunotoxicity, it is the carcinogenic and genotoxic (DNA-damaging) potential of these compounds that has attracted most attention. A number of PAHs have shown carcinogenicity in experimental animals and genotoxicity and mutagenicity *in vitro* and *in vivo*. Benzo(a)pyrene is a probable human carcinogen. Some other PAHs have also been identified as being carcinogens, with possible genotoxic properties. The high level of PAHS recorded in this study make the extracts potential carcinogens [32].

4. CONCLUSION

Aqueous wood ash extracts of *A. indica* and *P. biglobosa* still retain some phytochemical properties, even after combustion. The chemical analysis of these extracts contained concentrations of heavy metals and polycyclic hydrocarbons (PAHS) than the standard permissible limits. The concentrations of these chemicals differ with plants. These heavy metals are capable of causing damage to animal or human tissues or altering the system when consumed. The high concentrations of heavy metals in wood ash extracts may also have negative environmental impacts if not properly handled and disposed, because of possible leaching into underground and surface waters. Aqueous extract of *P. biglobosa* was corrosive and can cause injury when in contact with the skin or other soft body parts.

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